

Detecting muscle activation in surface electromyography

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Abstract. Surface electromyography (sEMG) is a non-invasive method for monitoring muscle activity, essential in rehabilitation, prosthetics, sports, and medicine. However, current sEMG systems struggle with signal noise, unclear muscle activation detection, and limited adaptability. This study proposes an innovative method combining advanced signal processing and machine learning to enhance muscle activation detection. Experiments with the Beyond EMG sensor show a significant accuracy improvement (up to 95%), highlighting potential applications in real-world biomedical settings.

Keywords: Surface electromyography, muscle activation, biomechanics, signal processing, machine learning, rehabilitation.

1 Introduction

Surface electromyography (sEMG) records muscle-generated electrical signals; as such, it is widely used in biomechanics, rehabilitation, and assistive technology to monitor muscle activity [1-2]. Despite its advantages, sEMG systems often suffer from signal noise, unclear activation detection, and limited adaptability to physiological variations [3-4]. To address these issues, this study integrates signal processing techniques—such as filtering, rectification, RMS envelope extraction, and thresholding—with machine learning models (Random Forest, XGBoost) to improve accuracy and reliability. Experiments on EMG data from biceps contractions demonstrated accuracies of 97% for the right biceps and 95% for the left, with an average recall of 96%, significantly outperforming traditional methods. This approach supports improved applications in rehabilitation, prosthetics, and sports science.

2 Material and Methods

This study analyzed a signal obtained through a Beyond EMG sensor with three electrodes placed on users' upper arms. To obtain functional signals with clear muscle activation and deactivation to be used as ground truth, a timed weight-lifting exercise (Fig. 1a-b) has been performed to generate a sample signal with three repetitions (Fig. 1c), repeated for three users. Then, a streamlined post-processing method has been

adopted to clarify these signals. After baseline correction to remove constant offsets, rectification was used to convert values to positive magnitudes.

Fig. 1. EMG signal processing for a weightlifting test: a. EMG sensor setup; b. Exercise for muscle activation; c. Resulting signal.

3 Analytical methods for muscle activation

After the preliminary post-processing described above, a root mean square (RMS) envelope was calculated over a moving window, smoothing fluctuations and highlighting muscle activity levels. Different values of samples and thresholds have been tested, both in absolute value (mV) and change rate (mV/s), with optimal results obtained for a 50-sample moving window and a threshold value of 0.095 mV/s on change rate, as

shown in Fig. 2d. The other tests highlight the general errors observed in EMG sensor analysis, with false positives in Fig. 2a and false negatives in Fig. 2c.

Unfortunately, these results proved to be sample-dependent, as different samples and acquisitions show different optimal values of thresholds. Overall, this analytical threshold-based method provided a simple and reliable approach for identifying muscle activation without relying on machine learning but requires manual calibration for each set of samples. Further, its effectiveness diminishes under high-noise or variable physiological conditions, suggesting the potential benefit of integrating AI techniques for further improvement. Finally, the moving window introduces delays in activation time that reduce overall sensor effectiveness, especially in online usage (e.g., exoskeleton control).

Fig. 2. Muscle activation identified with analytical methods, using different threshold values at signal rate of change.

4 AI-based detection methods for muscle activation

To further improve muscle detection accuracy, machine learning methods were integrated in the signal analysis pipeline, using Random Forest and XGBoost classifiers. Preprocessing steps included baseline correction to remove offsets and Wiener and Butterworth filtering to reduce noise. Key features capturing both time-domain (RMS, MAV, waveform length) and frequency-domain (median frequency, spectral entropy) characteristics were extracted from the filtered signals.

To address class imbalance in the dataset, Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) was applied during model training, ensuring balanced representation of muscle states. The trained models demonstrated strong performance, achieving detection accuracies of 97% for the right biceps, 95% for the left biceps, and an average recall of 96%, outperforming threshold-based methods and easily adapting to highly variable signals such as the one in Fig. 3 below.

The AI-based approach provides a more adaptive and robust solution for sEMG analysis, particularly effective in noisy conditions and with signal variability. It lays the groundwork for real-time systems in rehabilitation, prosthetics, and biomechanics applications.

Fig. 3. Muscle activation identified with AI-based methods.

5 Conclusions

This study developed a framework for analyzing surface electromyography (sEMG) signals to improve muscle activation detection. By integrating baseline correction, rectification, RMS envelope extraction, and thresholding, the signal processing approach reduced noise and highlighted activation patterns. However, traditional threshold-based methods can struggle with adaptability in complex or noisy conditions. To overcome these limitations, machine learning models such as Random Forest and XGBoost were introduced. By using key time-domain and frequency-domain features, these AI-based

methods significantly enhanced classification accuracy and robustness. The combined approach achieved high performance levels, offering a reliable method for muscle activation analysis. These findings contribute to advancing sEMG applications in rehabilitation, sports performance monitoring, and prosthetics. Future research could extend this work to additional muscle groups and explore real-time, wireless solutions to improve practical usability in clinical and biomechanical settings.

References

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